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Needs, challenges, and opportunities identified in EIRENE PPP

Following the development of the Scientific vision, mission, and agenda within T1.1, we identified capacities to be developed and outlined the desired EIRENE Architecture based on the service pillars (D1.2). At the same time, we performed an inventory of the capacities available in the EIRENE consortium, categorised them into pillar structure and the structure of central and national nodes(D2.1). This served as a baseline for outlining the Roadmap for further development of central and national services (D2.2).

The documents outlining the data management and quality assessment procedures were also developed: Data policy and management plan (D3.1), ELSA Guidelines (D3.2), Report on data collection and generation (D3.3), and a Report on data access and sharing (D3.4).

Last but not least, we outlined the open access system, e.g., prepared EIRENE RI Access procedures to be tested (D4.1), identified EIRENE RI facilities to be used in the Pilot (D4.2), and drafted EIRENE RI pilot design and tools (D4.3). EIRENE RI Service Access rules & procedures were also developed (D2.3).

All these efforts fed into the development of this Technical design development plan (D1.3), which summarizes which of the desired services are most readily available, how they are distributed across the national nodes, and which of them will be made available via the central open-access system in the first phase of the EIRENE implementation. This document will also serve as a base for outlining the strategy for upscaling and harmonisation of provided services, the development of novel technologies and integrative services in the next phases of EIRENE implementation.

D2.3	EIRENE RI Service Access rules & procedures	WP2	UU	R	PU	30
D3.4	Report on data access and sharing	WP3	CNR	R	PU	32

EIRENE Scientific Concept and Service Pillars

The scientific vision and the scope of capacities for exposomics to be developed and/or integrated were defined within EIRENE PPP. These include mobilising existing large-scale **geospatial and satellite data** to be used for the characterisation of external exposures. To construct detailed (personal) external exposure profiles of target populations, they should be combined with advanced tools (**micro-samplers and wearable sensor technologies for continuous monitoring**), collecting high-resolution spatial and temporal data in real time. Harmonised characterisation of internal exposures requires **high-throughput infrastructural platforms integrating state-of-the-art mass spectrometry with AI-driven analytical tools** addressing the extensive spectrum of exogenous exposure markers, including chemicals of concern, and endogenous effect markers. The toxicity of chemical mixtures found in biological tissues must be evaluated using **innovative hazard characterisation and toxicity testing platforms**, including high-throughput platforms employing New Approach Methodologies (NAMs) for testing the safety of chemicals, and exposure simulation chambers. This provides data for the development of **Adverse Outcome Pathways (AOPs)**,

improving mechanistic understanding of biological responses and **next-generation risk assessment tools** integrating exposure and hazard data into predictive models that better capture the complexity of real-world exposures. A wide spectrum of exogenous (exposure) and endogenous (effect) markers identified in high-resolution data from emerging mass-spec technologies enables the assessment of associations between exposures and effects. These technologies - when harmonised and employed in systematic population studies where their results can be combined with additional external exposure data (**natural, built-in, and social environments, occupation, lifestyle, diet**), **genomic** (and other *-omic*) data and **longitudinal clinical/health records** - can significantly advance our mechanistic understanding of disease development and identify factors playing major roles in this process.

To achieve EIRENE’s objectives and ambitions and enable challenge-driven research linking environmental factors to human health, we need to integrate the necessary capacities in the multi-dimensional infrastructural matrix consisting of (i) **longitudinal observation cohorts** (birth, child, adult, occupational, ageing), **cross-cutting biomonitoring and health surveys, and clinical studies** (including biobanks); **harmonised experimental capacities and leading-edge innovative technologies** to assess (ii) **internal exposures** and their biological effects, (iii) **external environmental exposures** by combining personal sensors with monitoring and satellite data, (iv) **hazards** and (v) **risks** associated with toxic chemicals and their mixtures, as well as (vi) research **environments for integrating** individual-level clinical, environmental and social datasets with geospatial data, advanced models and data interpretation tools (including tools for the safe governance and management of sensitive data, their harmonisation, and federated analyses) bridging disciplinary divides and providing integrated services to empower European research linking environmental exposures to human health (Figure 1).

Figure 1: EIRENE ambitions (right) and domains of necessary infrastructural capacities: population studies (left), experimental, technological and computational capacities for internal and external exposure, hazard and risk assessment (bottom), and research environments and tools for data integration and interpretation (top)

Progress in the development of EIRENE capacities and national nodes

At the time of establishment, the **EIRENE consortium** was composed of institutions from 16 European countries signing the Memorandum of Understanding. They included the Czech Republic (the coordinating country), Austria, Belgium, Greece, Germany, Iceland, Italy, the Netherlands, and Slovakia (countries providing the political support), Finland, France, Norway, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, and the UK. During the preparatory phase, additional countries (Cyprus, Denmark, Luxembourg, Portugal, and Switzerland) joined the consortium. The EIRENE ambition, however, goes beyond Europe. While the US partners were part of the original consortium, those from Australia, Canada, and Japan joined in the preparatory phase, bringing the number of participating countries to 25. The EIRENE consortium also collaborates with EMBL-EBI.

The levels of preparedness of participating institutions vary significantly in the individual countries. The most advanced is the **EIRENE coordination hub** (RECETOX RI) at Masaryk University (Czechia). It has been established as the large national infrastructure for research and innovation and included in the national roadmap already in 2011, and therefore, has a long history of providing services. It provides the physical, remote and virtual access to (i) samples and data from 3 in-house longitudinal population cohorts (CELSPAC, TNG, HAPIEE), (ii) capacities of accredited trace analytical laboratories, biomarker laboratories (high-resolution mass spectroscopy enabling target and non-target metabolomics and proteomics) and metagenomic laboratories, including bioinformatic capacities for analysis of resulting mass spec and sequencing data), (iii) data from the international MONET air and water monitoring networks, and (iv) in-house databases, expertise in ontologies, data stewardship and FAIR data management practices, informatic and bioinformatic tools. Every year, RECETOX RI provides access to hundreds of users via its electronic open-access system. Thousands of samples are being analysed remotely, but many person-months are also provided for the physical access and training of users, including students internationally. The international summer school is being organised on an annual basis together with a long list of training courses offered to international institutions (UNEP, WHO), projects, and individuals. RECETOX RI capacities are developed and access enabled through the financial support provided by the Czech Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports (MEYS), responsible for the RI (and ESFRI) agenda in Czechia (the support is provided based on the regular international evaluation, currently secured until December 2026). At the end of the preparatory/beginning of the implementation period, MEYS reconfirmed its intent to host the future EIRENE ERIC and financially support the establishment of the coordination hub. The implementation phase project proposal was submitted in September 2025, and the RECETOX RI proposal for the MEYS support for the 2027-2024 period will be submitted in December 2025. The RECETOX RI open access system will be scaled up to enable access to all EIRENE services at the beginning of the EIRENE implementation period (the OA system architecture was developed and piloted in the EIRENE PPP). In addition to the coordination of the development of EIRENE services and provision of open access to them (including the development, maintenance, and updating of the service catalogues), the EIRENE coordination hub at MU is expected to take responsibility for legal and ethical aspects of the future ERIC, harmonisation procedures, and quality assurance/quality control frameworks.

A detailed inventory of relevant service capacities was performed in the EIRENE PPP across multiple institutions in participating countries, with a special focus on services readily available for open access. Most national nodes in 9 countries with the political support managed to secure some national funding to develop their capacities (Austria, Belgium,

Czechia, Greece, Germany, Italy, and the Netherlands) and are ready to start providing services (Iceland and Slovakia reconfirmed their interest to be among the EIRENE ERIC founding countries, but are not yet providing services). Service capacities were, however, also developed in other countries from the original EIRENE consortium, especially France, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, and the UK (these countries are also expected to provide political support for ERIC in the next phase). In Finland, Norway, and countries joining EIRENE recently (Denmark, Portugal), such an inventory of service capacities still has to be finalised. However, some services were already made available in countries that joined EIRENE in the preparatory phase, namely in Cyprus, Luxembourg, and Switzerland. From the non-European countries, Canada and the US are also making their facilities available for open access. Altogether, we expect to enable access to research infrastructures in 17 countries in the EIRENE implementation phase. More information on the round of services to be made available is provided in the next section and summarised in the annex Table. More service capacities will be developed during the implementation phase, including those already participating as well as new countries.

The **Austrian node** of EIRENE (“Exposome Austria”), coordinated by the University of Vienna, provides advanced analytical and biomedical services, with Open Labs in Vienna and Innsbruck linked to mass spectrometry facilities. Together with the Environment Agency Austria, it analyses biological and environmental samples to assess chemical exposure and its effects using cutting-edge methods. It focuses on the development and offering of innovative mass spectrometry-based analytical services in the areas of Next-generation human biomonitoring (HBM), Non-targeted analysis (biological and environmental matrices), and Multi-metal and multi-PFAS analysis. In the first phase, only the Vienna University opens its capacities for TNA.

The EIRENE node in **Belgium** opens capacities of VITO (Flemish Institute for Technological Research, the coordinator), Catholic University Leuven (KUL), and University of Antwerp. VITO (<https://vito.be/en>) provides advanced in vitro inhalation testing, molecular analysis (ICP-MS, LC-MS, PCR), and high-throughput Olink proteomics for biomarker discovery in human and mouse samples. Its PEH Data Platform makes human biomonitoring data FAIR and accessible for exposome research. Terrascope, Belgium’s Earth Observation Dataspace, offers easy access to Copernicus Sentinel satellite data via viewers, cloud tools, and a service marketplace. Open-access services include In-Vitro Inhalation Platform - Realistic inhalation exposures with air-liquid interface-cultured lung models; Supports safety & efficacy testing; Reduces reliance on animal testing; Flexible study design; 2D and 3D lung models (healthy & diseased, incl. COPD, asthma, CF, smokers); Acute & repeated exposures, variable durations/concentration; Endpoints: viability, cytotoxicity, inflammation, oxidative stress, biomarkers, ciliary function, cellular uptake & translocation dynamics; Proven expertise; Tested complex substances: volatile compounds, reactive vapors, surfactants; Applied in real-world exposure scenarios; Technology innovation; NAVETTA patented exposure system for controlled, reproducible aerosol delivery. Olink proteomics - targeted protein quantification of the different Olink biomarker panels in a plethora of different samples from humans and mice. VITO also provides Virtual Access to the Personal Exposure & Health (PEH) Data Platform. The PEH Data Platform helps HBM study owners make data FAIR, GDPR-compliant, and visible by harmonizing, validating, and sharing metadata via public resources like the European HBM Dashboard. Researchers can securely access pseudonymous data to study trends and link to exposome information. By 2025, the platform hosts studies from 15+ countries and has granted access to 78 researchers from 25 institutions in 17 countries. Training and support are provided through a help desk. VITO Terrascope - Users have free

access to global maps of atmospheric gases (NO₂, CO, CH₄, HCHO, SO₂), advanced NO₂ maps for Europe (CAM5), and global Land Cover products from ESA WorldCover, CLM3, and Tropical Forest Mapping. Vegetation indicators are available from Sentinel-2 (10–20 m, EEA38, 2018–present) as well as global datasets from SPOT-VGT (1998–2014), PROBA-V (2014–2020), and Sentinel-3 (2020–present). Terrascope also provides free cloud processing via Jupyter Notebooks, Virtual Machines, and openEO (5,000 credits/month), along with additional EOplaza services (5,000 credits/month).

KUL (<https://www.humansentinel.net/en>) offers HSSP, a scalable, expert-backed platform for real-time occupational and environmental health monitoring, enabling proactive risk assessment and intervention. It supports data collection by health professionals and emphasizes the value of health records in promoting well-being. KU Leuven's CEH specializes in chemical exposure analysis using advanced techniques to assess air, surface, and biological samples. Their research links environmental contaminants to health outcomes, including epigenetic effects. RI offers an Analysis platform for targeted exposomics and epigenetics - Services include non-targeted and suspect screening for known and emerging substances in biological and environmental samples, LC-MS/MS analysis of cytostatics and pesticides in biospecimens, GC-FID for VOCs in air samples (with kits covering 180 compounds in one run), and epigenetic analysis. KUL also provides Virtual Access to the Human Sentinel Surveillance Platform (HSSP) - offers customizable training for health and safety professionals, engineers, and sentinels, covering platform use, SOPs, compliance, and data collection methods. It supports sector-specific hazard identification, digital surveys, and sentinel monitoring, including IoT and wearables for real-time exposure tracking. Advanced data collection includes standardized tools for exposure assessment, biomonitoring, and epidemiological surveillance. Data analysis is enhanced with AI-driven insights, supporting interventions and policy recommendations, while ensuring confidentiality and compliance with FAIR data principles.

The Toxicological Centre of the University of Antwerp (<https://www.uantwerpen.be/en/research-groups/toxicological-centre/>) specialises in targeted and non-targeted analysis of biomarkers in biological and environmental samples. Using advanced chromatographic and mass spectrometric techniques, it investigates chemical exposures and their health effects, supported by metabolomics tools. Access is provided to the LC-MSMS platform for targeted and untargeted exposomics and metabolomics - Services include LC-MS/MS analysis of PFAS, plasticizer metabolites, flame retardants, bisphenols, and pesticides; LC-HRMS suspect screening and non-target profiling of chemical biomarkers; targeted and untargeted metabolomics and lipidomics using LC-MS/MS and LC-HRMS; and workflows and resources for HRMS data processing.

The newly established EIRENE node in **Cyprus** opens access to CHILDREN_FIRST (www.childrenfirstcy.com), the Cyprus's exposomics-based cohort led by CUT and focused on environmental risk factors and health outcomes in school-aged children. It uses harmonized tools to assess respiratory, cardiometabolic, and neurodevelopmental effects over time. The platform supports EU-wide research on circadian-based health interventions and precision prevention, emphasizing gene–environment–lifestyle interactions for improved child health.

Access includes CHILDREN-FIRST cohort – Untargeted GC-MS/MS metabolomics of human samples; CHILDREN_FIRST cohort data and samples available for EU studies; Circadian rhythm biomarkers and health metrics; Design and implementation of personalized, non-pharmacological prevention trials, including chrono-regulated approaches; Algorithms for processing chrono-based longitudinal data.

As mentioned above, RECETOX RI ([Research Infrastructure \(RI\) | RECETOX](#)) in **Czechia** comprises core facilities including MONET air and water monitoring networks, CELSPAC population cohorts (www.celspac.cz), advanced biobanking, ISO 17025-accredited analytical laboratories, biomarker (omics), toxicological and microbiome labs, and bioinformatics platforms with Galaxy pipelines for high-resolution exposomics. Laboratory capacities include LC and GC/ICP-MS, HRGC/HRMS, GC/MSMS, HPLC/MSMS (ISO 17025-accredited), CO₂ incubators, high-end microscopes, microplate analyzers, PCR/RT-qPCR, electrophoresis, blotting setups, and permanent in vitro/in vivo cultures. Samples and data from four large-scale population studies, including the national COVID-19 seroprevalence study, are available. Virtual Access is provided to exposome cohort datasets (<https://www.recetox.muni.cz/en/services/celspac-population-studies>) and GENASIS database of environmental monitoring and human biomonitoring data. Virtual Access is also provided to computation tools, and trainings that support chemical exposomics, metabolomics, and proteomics mass spectrometry data processing. The RI provides technical support and training to external users and supports educational activities of the hosting RECETOX Centre, a WHO Collaborating Centre, the Stockholm Convention Regional Centre for Capacity Building and Technology Transfer in Central and Eastern Europe, and the Czech National Centre for Toxic Compounds. Services include access to the CELSPAC birth cohorts samples and data; Multiplex IgE testing (ALEX method); Automated extraction of DNA/RNA from different types of human matrices. Toxicology - The lab provides advanced toxicological screening and imaging, in vitro testing using stem cell models, and assessments of endocrine disruption, genotoxicity, and oxidative stress. It supports bioavailability and microbial activity analysis, reporter gene assays, and water quality monitoring. Ecotoxicological testing is conducted across aquatic and soil environments using diverse model organisms. The lab also performs health and environmental risk assessments, including occupational exposure and chemical safety evaluations. Biomarker Analytical Lab (BAL) - GC-HRMS anthropogenic profiling of human biospecimen; GC-HRMS metabolite profiling of biospecimen; LC-HRMS small molecule profiling of human biospecimen; Quantitation of inflammatory and immunity protein markers in human blood; Software, workflows and resources for processing HRMS data. Trace Analytical Lab (TAL) - offers the complete analytical services: the sampling of environmental matrices, the analytical method development across various domains upon customer request, the sample preparation and analysis, techniques for analysing pollutants in environmental and human matrices, including quality control. Microbiome Analytical Laboratories (MGL) - provides state-of-the-art infrastructure, expert support and service for metagenomic research which is essential to better understand the microbial communities that inhabit different ecosystems, including the human body, animals, models (organoids, biofilms,) and environmental samples (dust, air, soil, water, etc.). Our molecular geneticists, biologists, microbiologists, and data analysts are proficient in non-targeted "shotgun" whole metagenome sequencing (WMGS) and targeted sequencing of 16S and ITS rRNA amplicons. The facility also provides support for sample collection, storage, and processing, and quality control checks. Users can send samples for analysis or perform analyses themselves under RECETOX supervision. In 2024, over 12,000 analyses were conducted for external users, and the lab supported 900 person-days of incoming researchers.

The **French node** of EIRENE ("France Exposome") includes INSERM, EHESP, ONIRIS, and ANSES (<https://www.france-exposome.org>). It brings together capacities in environmental health to study chemical exposures using mass spectrometry, toxicokinetics, and predictive toxicology. ProMetHEE, ANSES's national platform, supports untargeted molecular analysis for food safety and toxicology. France Cohortes, launched in 2021, centralizes cohort management across 20 studies, promoting tool sharing and collaboration,

with plans for EU and international expansion. The hub provides access to Targeted quantitative analysis (LC-MS/MS, GC-MS/MS, IC-MS/MS, ICP-MS/MS) of environmental chemicals in human biospecimens; HRMS (LC- and GC-) suspect screening of human biospecimens; HRMS (LC- and GC-) non-targeted analysis of human biospecimens; Software, workflows and resources for processing HRMS data; PBKT modelling; Adverse Outcome Pathway tools for predictive toxicology. ANSES National Proteomics and Metabolomics Platform – ProMetHEE - Scientific and technical expertise for quantitative proteomics and untargeted metabolomics; Assistance in project definition, including experimental design, resource assessment, and risk analysis; Sample preparation from a wide variety of sources (cells, colonies, organoids, tissues, fluids, culture media, organs, organisms); Mass spectrometry analyses using nanoLC-ESI-QTOF HRMS; Data processing and re-analysis with robust bioinformatics workflows; Support for data interpretation and reporting; Guidance for data deposition into public repositories (e.g. PRIDE, Metabolights). INSERM also provides Virtual Access to France Cohorts, the platform offering a modular information system aligned with SNDS and EDS standards, supporting secure data collection, integration, analysis, and sharing. It offers regulatory support with compliant documentation templates, assistance in study design and participant engagement, and tools for FAIR data management, including cataloguing, documentation, and transparent governance. www.francecohortes.org

The **German node** of EIRENE, coordinated by the Helmholtz centre in Munich (<https://www.helmholtz-munich.de/en/>), focuses primarily on human cohorts (at HMGU, Leipzig University, and Regensburg) and, in the first phase, offers access to the German National Cohort (NAKO) (<https://nako.de/en/>). NAKO is Germany's largest health cohort, with over 205,000 participants recruited between 2014–2019 across 18 centers. It provides deep phenotyping, biosample collection (blood, urine, saliva, stool, nasal swabs), and whole-body MRI for a subset. Follow-ups occur regularly, with data stored in a central biobank under strict quality standards. NAKO supports research into disease causes and precision prevention, backed by 26 institutions and national funding. NAKO offers infrastructure for population-based health research, with longitudinal data and biosamples from over 205,000 participants. Resources include standardized health assessments, interviews, and questionnaires, plus a central biobank with high-quality samples for molecular analysis. Unique assets include whole-body 3T MRI for a sub-cohort, geocoded environmental data, and upcoming genomic data (genotyping and whole genome sequencing) by 2027. NAKO offers Virtual Access to the infrastructure for population-based health research, with longitudinal data and biosamples from over 205,000 participants.

EIRENE in **Greece** is represented by AUTH and NHRF (<https://www.eirene-el.gr/>). Greece's national exposome infrastructure brings together leading institutions to study environmental impacts on health. Led by Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, it supports data and sample collection, interdisciplinary research, and public engagement. The platform enables precision exposomics and fosters collaboration across academia, industry, and society. EIRENE-GR provides essential exposome services through six core platforms: access to biobanked samples and metadata for diverse cohort studies; design and implementation of biological and environmental sample collection; targeted and untargeted external and internal exposome analyses; advanced toxicity assessment using multi-omics, imaging, and micro/nanoplastics detection; and in-silico services via the INTEGRA System, including computational toxicology, multi-omics analysis, EWAS, ontology-based platforms, agent-based modelling, and systems biology for AOP development.

The **Italian node** is led by CNR (<https://www.ii.cnr.it>), hosting the Global Observation System for Mercury (GOS4M) Knowledge Hub (G-KH), a multi-model platform for analysing mercury contamination impacts on ecosystems and human health across spatial and temporal scales. It supports policy evaluation by modelling mercury fate—from sources to bioaccumulation in fish and atmospheric concentrations—and estimating socio-economic costs. It integrates atmospheric, oceanic, and ecological models to assess long-term trends. Complementing this, CNR-IIA conducts advanced environmental and health research with state-of-the-art labs for pollutant and mercury analysis, molecular biology, and climate monitoring. It also supports Italy's national air quality network with high-resolution data and regulatory-grade instrumentation. EIRENE Italy supports Biomonitoring and offers access to Environmental and Health Labs, enabling quantification of heavy metals, ionic species, and carbonaceous aerosol fractions (OC/EC) in environmental and biological matrices. It supports high-throughput mercury analysis across diverse sample types and provides access and training at the Monte Curcio GAW station for atmospheric research. CNR also provides Virtual Access to GOS4M Knowledge Hub, which offers high-quality and comparable data of mercury concentrations and fluxes in air, ocean, and terrestrial ecosystems; validated models to assess the fate of mercury in air and oceans; a fully integrated knowledge hub for assessing the effectiveness of policy measures by delivering information on reduction scenarios and cost-effective strategies. Data access is granted by a data catalogue and a GEO community portal. Specific widgets bring specialized and science-based analyses to the user's desk (<http://www.gos4m.org/>).

The Istituto Superiore di Sanità (ISS) (<https://www.iss-international.com/>) is Italy's leading public health research and advisory body, supporting policy through scientific evidence. It operates across multiple departments and centers and represents Italy in key European research infrastructures (BBMRI-ERIC, EATRIS-ERIC, ECRIN-ERIC, ELIXIR). While ISS does not currently maintain a certified biobank or clinical/epidemiological databases, it plays a central role in national and EU-level biomedical research. It opens access to the ISS Trace Labs offering advanced infrastructure for environmental and human biomonitoring, specializing in the analysis of persistent organic pollutants (POPs), trace elements, and nanoparticles. Services include targeted and non-targeted chemical analysis using GC-MS/MS, LC-MS/MS, HRMS, and ICP-MS technologies. Accredited methods support quantification of dioxins, PCBs, PFAS, heavy metals, and mercury in various matrices. The lab also provides isotopic ratio and speciation analysis, nanoparticle characterization, and supports national and EU-level research projects with validated workflows and high-end instrumentation.

The EIRENE node in **Luxembourg** has recently been established around the Laboratoire National de Santé (www.lns.lu), specialised in medical analysis, public health surveillance, and research. Its ENVIROH service analyses human samples (blood, urine, hair) for exposure and effect biomarkers and conducts indoor environmental testing under ISO accreditation. The MEDI service supports environmental and occupational health assessments, manages national science-policy programs (e.g., HBM4EU, PARC), and leads epidemiological surveys in collaboration with the National Hospital Service. In the first phase, the Department of Health Protection (DHP) offers access to the platform supporting human biomonitoring through advanced analysis of VOC metabolites, heavy metals, PFAS, phthalates, pesticides, bisphenols, and flame retardants in biological matrices using state-of-the-art instrumentation. Indoor chemistry services include air and dust sample analysis for VOCs, aldehydes, NO₂, and various pollutants. Microbiological services cover the detection and identification of airborne and surface fungi and bacteria, as well as allergen quantification in dust.

Utrecht University coordinates the EIRENE node in the Netherlands (<https://exposome.nl/>) and provides access to the AMIGO (Occupational and Environmental Health Prospective Cohort Study), PIAMA (Prevention and Incidence of Asthma and Mite Allergy), and Nightingale cohorts, the large-scale Dutch studies offering rich data on environmental, occupational, and lifestyle exposures. AMIGO includes 14,829 adults with detailed exposure and health records via GP databases. PIAMA (<https://piama.iras.uu.nl/en/>) follows ~3,963 children from birth into adulthood, investigating asthma, allergy, and lung function with repeated questionnaires, clinical exams, and environmental sampling. AMIGO and PIAMA data can be obtained through the submission of a data request. Nightingale (<https://nightingale-studie.nl/>) tracks 59,947 female nurses with extensive job history, shift work data, and genetic samples, focusing on chronic disease outcomes. Biological samples (toenails for DNA analysis) and follow-up data linked to national registries support research on circadian disruption and chronic disease. Data access is available via formal request, with active support for circadian health research. The Exposome Maps platform complements these cohorts by providing high-resolution geospatial data on built, food, physico-chemical, and social environments across Europe, enabling GDPR-compliant linkage with GPS data for exposome research. Exposome Maps (data platform) - Exposome Maps offers geospatial services for environmental exposure research through an online platform featuring detailed exposome surfaces across Europe. It provides data in four dimensions—built, food, physico-chemical, and social environments—with over 200 variables. Users can explore maps, access metadata, and link GPS data in a GDPR-compliant manner.

Wageningen University (Wageningen Food Safety Research, WFSR) focuses on exposure assessment of known and unknown toxicants across the food–environment–human axis. Using ISO17025-accredited LC-MS/MS, GC-MS/MS, and high-resolution screening (LC/GC-HRMS), it analyzes diverse samples—food, urine, blood, hair, dust, soil—to understand external and internal chemical exposure and pathways. The platform supports quantitative analysis of pesticides, natural toxins, POPs, and exposure biomarkers using LC-MS/MS and GC-MS/MS. It enables targeted, suspect, and non-target screening of toxicants in human matrices via LC-HRMS and GC-HRMS and provides workflows and resources for high-resolution mass spectrometry (HRMS) data processing.

At the Vrije Universiteit (VU) Amsterdam, the Histology Lab prepares biological tissues for microscopic analysis with full histopathology capabilities. The HT-EDA platform enables high-throughput effect-directed analysis by combining precise LC fractionation (via FractioMate®), miniaturized bioassays, and advanced HRMS/IMS for identifying bioactive contaminants. The VU-MS facilities support targeted and non-targeted screening of organic contaminants in diverse samples, using MS, HRMS, TIMS, and integrated data pipelines for exposure assessment and metabolomics. The histology infrastructure provides end-to-end histopathology services, including automated tissue processing, paraffin embedding, precision sectioning, high-throughput staining, and digital slide scanning. Diagnostic support is available through expert histopathological evaluation of scanned slides. VU Platform for high-throughput effect-directed analysis offers high-resolution fractionation of environmental and biological samples using liquid chromatography, with global delivery of dried plates. Bioactivity testing is available through assays targeting endocrine disruption, tyrosine kinase inhibition, microbial resistance, and developmental toxicity in zebrafish embryos. Active fractions are analysed via HRMS, with optional ion mobility separation and in silico prioritization using QSAR models. VU MS Platform for targeted and non-target analysis (exposomics / metabolomics) - The infrastructure provides advanced chemical and omics analysis, including quantification of micro/nanoplastics (Py-GC-MS), targeted analysis of PFAS, additives, and steroids (LC-MS/MS), and suspect/non-target screening of contaminants

(LC-HRMS). It supports both targeted and non-targeted metabolomics and lipidomics, with automated HRMS data workflows and machine learning for feature prioritization.

University of Leiden (<https://exposome.nl/scan/>) opens access to the infrastructure supporting mechanism-based hazard assessment using transcriptomics in human cell models (e.g. liver, kidney, pancreas). It provides FAIR high-throughput data via the TXG-MAPr platform, building on EU-ToxRisk and RISK-HUNT3R. The Exposome-Scan platform combines metabolomics and exposomics using MS-based workflows and advanced computational pipelines. Novel technologies like single-cell and spatial MS imaging are integrated to support exposome research across the Netherlands. The infrastructure offers treatment of 2D and 3D test systems using primary and iPSC-derived models of liver, kidney, heart, and mammary gland, combined with cytotoxicity and transcriptomics analysis. It provides transcriptional PODs and full support from study design to data interpretation. Advanced profiling platforms enable targeted and untargeted metabolite, lipid, and small molecule analysis. In-house software ensures data quality and integration, supported by a robust small molecule identification pipeline. The facility is closely linked to Exposome Scan (LACDR) and the EU-BioImaging HTM node at Leiden University. ULEI Exposome Scan provides high-throughput metabolomics and exposomics services through validated targeted and untargeted assays covering a wide range of small molecules, including drugs, pollutants, and nutritional compounds. The infrastructure supports end-to-end workflows—from study design to data interpretation—and integrates environmental exposure data (e.g. air pollution) with molecular profiles. Advanced mass spectrometry platforms enable inflammation, gut, and brain metabolism studies, with innovations in extracellular vesicle analysis and spatially resolved MS. Multi-omics analysis is supported through collaborations with other national partners such as IRAS, Erasmus MC, and LUMC.

University Groningen operates the Genomics Coordination Center (GCC) at UMCG enabling large-scale genomics and exposome research across national and EU projects. Its 40-member team manages data infrastructure and analysis, operating the MOLGENIS cloud for FAIR data, secure HPC environments (TRE4HPC), federated analysis (DataSHIELD), and expert support. GCC runs over 100 database servers and multiple HPC instances with 1.5 PB storage, >1000 CPU cores, and 6 GPUs, supporting projects like Solve-RD, Lifelines, and EJP-RD. Key platforms include BBMRI-ERIC Directory, EHEN catalogue, and FAIR Genomes NL. The UMCG MOLGENIS FAIR data cloud offers modular FAIR data management via MOLGENIS, including customizable databases, web interfaces, and FAIR endpoints. It provides a Trusted HPC environment (TRE4HPC) for secure, large-scale analysis of sensitive human data, and supports federated analysis through DataSHIELD/Armadillo networks. Additional services include support for NGS pipelines (WES, WGS, RNA), database setup, and software containerization, available through prepaid support tickets.

RIVM provides access to the Monte Carlo Risk Assessment (MCRA) (<https://mcra.rivm.nl/mcra/#/>), a web-based platform with over 50 modules for assessing health risks from chemical mixtures via food, air, and skin exposure. It supports hazard identification, exposure assessment, and risk evaluation using models aligned with EU and EFSA guidelines, as well as novel scientific approaches. In the PARC project, MCRA is widely used across EU Member States to assess real-life mixtures using human biomonitoring data (internal exposure).

MCRA supports mixture risk assessment through internal exposure analysis using human biomonitoring data and external exposure modelling based on food, air, and emission data. It offers kinetic modelling to compare internal and external exposures, and health impact or burden of disease modelling. Users have access to the MCRA data platform and receive support via a dedicated help desk. <https://mcra.rivm.nl/mcra/#/>.

Jozef Stefan Institute (JSI) in Ljubljana coordinates the EIRENE node in **Slovenia** (www.environment.si). Slovenia's national exposome node, integrates chemical analytics, omics, biobanking, digital infrastructure, and citizen science into a unified platform. It supports targeted and non-targeted screening, omics (genomics, metabolomics, microbiomics, proteomics), and FAIR data management, enabling comprehensive assessment of environmental and lifestyle impacts on human health. Targeted and non-targeted chemical exposure assessment in human and environmental samples; stable isotope and speciation analysis for tracing exposure sources; biobanking and access to biological samples and metadata; omics-based biomarker discovery and toxicological testing; data integration and modelling using PBPK, QSAR, and AI for chemical mixture risk assessment; citizen science platforms for participatory data collection and protocol co-design; and training and education through the EIRENE Virtual Lab, summer schools, doctoral programmes, and secondments.

The EIRENE node in **Spain** brings together population cohort resources of ISGlobal in Barcelona in with the environmental research capacities of CSIC and environmental health expertise of the ISCIII institute in Madrid. The resources of the HELIX cohort are ready to be opened to the research community via EIRENE open access (<https://athleteproject.eu/helix-cohort/>). The HELIX cohort integrates data from six European birth cohorts (France, Greece, Lithuania, Norway, Spain, UK), covering 1,663 mother-child pairs with biomarkers, multi-omics, and health outcomes measured at ages 6–11 and 12–17. It also includes panel studies with ~150 children and ~150 pregnant women for personal exposure assessment. HELIX data can be obtained through the submission of a data request, following the HELIX Data External Data Request Procedures (<http://www.projecthelix.eu/index.php/es/data-inventory>). The HELIX data infrastructure has been extensively used for early-life exposome studies, by international organizations.

The EIRENE node in **Sweden** is coordinated by Örebro University (<https://www.oru.se/mtm>). ORU at the MTM Research Centre offers five integrated installations for chemical and bioanalytical research, supporting national agencies and EU projects. Facilities include advanced mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS, GC-MS/MS, HRMS) for pollutant analysis, effect-based bioassays for endocrine and genotoxic activity, and Effect-Directed Analysis (EDA) using LC/GC fractionation. In vivo models (zebrafish, earthworms) assess toxicity, while Exposome analysis combines metabolomics and contaminant screening with bioinformatics for human health research. MTM offers mass spectrometry-based quantification of micropollutants and suspect screening, with specialized PFAS assays (total fluorine, extractable fluorine, oxidizable precursors). Services include iceberg/mass balance modelling, toxicity prediction, and effect-based methods to support toxicant discovery. Zebrafish embryo-based test systems are available for toxicity and behavioural studies. The infrastructure also provides analytical and computational tools for metabolomics and exposome research linking environmental exposures to health outcomes.

The Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences (SLU) in Uppsala (<https://www.slu.se>) offers a unique platform for comparative developmental biology in mammals and aquatic species. Facilities support embryo production, controlled exposures, behavioral tracking, and histological analysis. The EDA platform, a collaboration between VoM and BVF, combines LC/GC fractionation, bioassays, and HRMS to identify toxic drivers in complex samples. The labs analyse (semi-)persistent organic pollutants (e.g. PFAS, pesticides, pharmaceuticals) in environmental matrices using LC-MS, GC-MS, and Orbitrap systems, supported by advanced sample prep and national monitoring networks. SLU supports DNA/RNA adductomics - the infrastructure provides targeted and untargeted DNA/RNA adductomics using HRMS-based

spectral matching and fragmentation analysis. Services include primary data analysis, biomarker discovery consulting, and statistical evaluation using multivariate and machine learning methods. Support is offered for threshold derivation and exposure assessment in humans and wildlife. Transparent, reproducible workflows are ensured through open tools and databases, with optional FAIR-compliant data deposition. Access is available via collaboration, fee-for-service, or proposal-based entry. SLU Developmental Biology Platform - The platform offers in vitro embryo production and evaluation for multiple species (cow, pig, cat, zebrafish, Xenopus, mollusc), with in vivo follow-up for aquatic models. Services include comparative cross-species testing, experimental design support, and full project execution. Additional capabilities include cryopreservation, fluorescent staining for microscopy, RNA and epigenetic analyses, embryo transfer (bovine), and culture media analysis. Zebrafish embryo-based toxicity and behavioural testing is available using EthoVision® tracking software. SLU EDA (effect direct analysis) platform - advanced effect-directed analysis (EDA) services for environmental samples, including screening of known and unknown contaminants, mixture toxicity assessment, and identification of toxicity drivers. It is primarily applied to water samples (e.g., wastewater, stormwater, drinking water) and supports both bioassay and chemical analyses. Users may send samples for analysis or conduct supervised secondments. The platform collaborates with public and private stakeholders to support pollutant monitoring and reduction strategies. SLU Water pollution analysis (target/nontarget) - supports target, suspect, and non-target screening of environmental samples, primarily water (e.g., wastewater, stormwater, drinking water), but also soil, sediment, plants, and biota. It contributes to national PFAS monitoring and pollutant research in aquatic and terrestrial environments. Services include method development, chemical analysis, and bioassays. Users may submit samples for analysis or conduct supervised secondments. The platform collaborates with environmental authorities, academia, municipalities, and industry.

Stockholm University (www.aces.su.se) opens access to the DNA/RNA Adductomics Facility and Ecotoxicological Effect Assessment Facility (ACES) providing advanced platforms for exposome research. Adductomics links chemical exposures to molecular changes in wildlife and humans using LC-MS/MS, HRMS, and in-house tools like nLossFinder. The ecotoxicology lab develops biomarkers across aquatic species, integrating omics into EU regulatory frameworks (MSFD, WFD, HELCOM, OSPAR) to assess ecosystem and human health. The National Facility for Exposomics at SciLifeLab (Campus Solna), coordinated by ACES, offers high-resolution chemical exposomics for diverse sample types. It supports targeted and untargeted analysis using open science tools, ensuring FAIR data practices and broad accessibility for national and international researchers. (<https://www.scilifelab.se/units/exposomics/>). SU Biomarker Labs provides analytical services including embryo development analysis, biochemical and molecular biomarkers (e.g. oxidative stress, neurotoxicity, gene expression), and integration of biomarker and contaminant data. Data services include threshold calculations, biomarker scoring, and statistical evaluation using multivariate and machine learning methods. Access to environmental metadata enables contextual interpretation and ecosystem-level assessments. Consulting and training are offered for protocol development, biomarker innovation, and capacity building through workshops and hands-on sessions. SU National Facility for Exposomics, Science for Life Laboratory - The infrastructure offers flexible chemical exposome services tailored to research needs, including ultratrace sample preparation for human biofluids and environmental samples. Analytical capabilities include LC/GC-HRMS with Orbitrap technology, combining targeted and non-targeted acquisition (DDA/DIA) and advanced ionization methods. Services cover structural elucidation of unknown compounds,

in-line solid phase extraction, multivariate data analysis, and FAIR-compliant workflows using open-source tools.

The EIRENE node in **Switzerland** was established recently by the University of Geneva (<https://farma-unites.unige.ch/en/rudaz-lab>). The Biomedical and Metabolomics Analysis Lab uses LC-MS-based approaches to study biochemical responses to toxicants. It offers steroid profiling and untargeted metabolomics/lipidomics in cell models, supporting research on toxicity mechanisms and Adverse Outcome Pathways. The steroidomics platform includes a library of over 200 endogenous steroids for comprehensive endocrine analysis. The metabolomics/lipidomics platform focuses on cell-based profiling for toxicology, including energy metabolism, oxidative stress, and apoptosis. The lab supports internal, national (e.g. projects with the Swiss Center of Applied Toxicology, funded through 2028), and international research.

University of Birmingham (UoB) (<https://www.birmingham.ac.uk/>) coordinates the development of the EIRENE node in the **United Kingdom**. UoB has long championed FAIR data practices, contributing core ontologies (e.g., AberOWL, PATO), and embedding FAIR principles into research workflows through tools like electronic lab notebooks and study design maps. UoB offers tailored FAIRification services developed through NanoCommons, WorldFAIR, and PARC. It also leads in Medical Concept Normalisation (MCN), using semantic search and LLMs to standardize biomedical and toxicological terms, supporting in silico NAMs and Adverse Outcome Pathway validation. UoB's toxicology platform includes advanced 3D organ-on-chip models, Daphnia and plant-based systems, and soil microbiome analysis, alongside world-class metabolomics and exposomics services via the Phenome Centre Birmingham, which contributes to OECD guidance and policy development. Ecotoxicity services include acute, chronic, reproductive, genotoxicity, endocrine disruption, and bioaccumulation assessments across a range of environmentally relevant species, enabling cross-species comparisons to identify conserved ancestral pathways. Assay development and optimization are provided to investigate mechanisms of action or validate specific Adverse Outcome Pathways for chemicals or particles. New assays are created using innovative endpoints such as lipid deposits and behavioural responses, with data generation supporting QSAR and PBPK modelling. Services also include sample generation for omics analyses—transcriptomics, proteomics, metabolomics—and assay miniaturization to increase throughput for chemical effect screening. UoB New-approach methodology (including organ-on-a-chip toxicity assay) development and benchmarking - Custom organ-on-chip services include design of microfluidic chip specifications and assay parameters, 3D printing and fabrication, cell culturing and seeding (human, rodent, fish), validation of organ or barrier functionality, uptake and toxicity testing with various chemicals and particles, and data analysis with FAIR data management support. Analytical services of the Phenome Centre Birmingham include UHPLC–MS platforms (Orbitrap Exploris, Orbitrap ID-X) for untargeted metabolomics, lipidomics, exposomics, and targeted biomarker analysis; hybrid approaches for simultaneous measurement of exposure chemicals and biochemical responses; automated sample preparation for diverse sample types; advanced workflows and spectral libraries for metabolite identification; high-performance computing for standardized data processing and analysis; and full project support from study design to reporting. Metadata and data management services provided by the UoB Toxicology and Ecotoxicology include customization of data capture templates aligned with OECD standards, generation of metadata schemas and crosswalks to preferred repositories, ontology development for assays and toxicity pathways, concept normalization using semantic enrichment and large language models, integration of existing tools via APIs or containers, and implementation of machine-actionable data management plans aligned with EIRENE and CRA Hub frameworks.

From the non-European partners, Columbia University has been the EIRENE consortium member since the preparatory phase. As the coordinator of **the US** project NEXUS, it now provides connections to other NEXUS partners (www.nexus-exposomics.org). For the initial phases of the EIRENE implementation, Columbia University and PNNL (<https://www.pnnl.gov/biology>) are opening an access to their facilities to the international research community. Columbia University, in partnership with PNNL, focuses on advancing measurement, modelling, and health applications. NEXUS supports NIH-funded efforts to build frameworks for biological, environmental, and geospatial exposomics, aiming to enable exposome-wide association studies (ExWAS). The initiative collaborates globally to establish integrated digital, biological, and spatial standards for precision environmental health. Columbia and PNNL offer extensive high-resolution mass spectrometry capabilities, including Orbitrap and SLIM-based systems, enabling broad chemical coverage without prior analyte selection. Their platforms support both polar and non-polar metabolite analysis, detection of novel xenobiotics, and identification of uncharacterized contaminants. Complementary tools from the Geospatial and Data Sciences Hubs support exposome-wide association studies (ExWAS) through containerized software and advanced analytics for exposomics research. The Biological Science Division at PNNL comprises 17 teams across four groups, conducting DOE- and NIH-funded research in multi-omics, systems biology, microbiomes, disease, and exposure science. Key assets include 23 advanced mass spectrometers (GC-MS, LC-MS, Orbitraps) and 800 MHz NMR, plus robust computational tools and decades of staff expertise in molecular measurements and data integration. BST at PNNL provides access to Untargeted LC-MS-based proteomics; Targeted LC-MS-based proteomics; Untargeted GC-MS-based metabolomics. Statistical analysis of omics data for biomarkers and data trends is also offered, as well as Multi-omics data integration and analysis; Advanced, interactive data visualization; Biological pathway enrichment and analysis.

In the last year of the preparatory phase, EIRENE consortium expanded also to **Canada** with University of Alberta (<https://www.tmicwishartnode.ca/services/?page=2>) taking a lead. The Wishart Laboratory at the University of Alberta is a leading North American centre for metabolomics and exposomics, forming part of Canada's Metabolomics Innovation Center (TMIC) network. Spanning 7,900 ft² across four specialized labs and equipped with over €8 million in instruments, it holds ISO/IEC 17025 and ISO 15189 certifications, ensuring high-quality, clinically relevant metabolomics analysis under rigorous standards. The Wishart Node of TMIC provides standardized quantitative metabolomics for diverse sample types, along with specialized exposomics assays and kits for pollutants, contaminants, metals, and microbiome-derived metabolites. Its Exposome 1.0 assay uses targeted LC-MS to measure a broad panel of environmental and dietary biomarkers, while Exposome 2.0 streamlines workflows for higher throughput, sensitivity, and cost-efficiency in large-scale studies. The Exposome 3.0 assay extends coverage to 400+ metabolites, including pesticides, PFAS, phthalates, VOCs, flame retardants, phenols, and parabens, offering a low-cost, high-throughput NHANES-like platform for exposome profiling. Wishart Node of TMIC) provides also Virtual Access to a wide range of open-access databases and web tools supporting metabolomics, exposomics, and natural products research. Key resources include MiMeDB for microbiome-derived metabolites, NP-MRD for NMR spectra of natural products, HMDB for human metabolites, DarkNPS for designer drugs, T3DB for toxins and chemicals, MarkerDB for clinical biomarkers, and ContaminantDB for environmental contaminants. Computational tools include LC-AutoFit for LC-MS data analysis, BioTransformer for

predicting biotransformations, CFM-ID for MS/MS spectrum interpretation, and Exposome Explorer for biomarkers of exposure.

At the later stage, we also count on connecting the Canadian cohorts as well as cohorts from other EIRENE nodes, such as Japan.

EIRENE also collaborates with EMBL-EBI and its Proteomics and Metabolomics installations (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metabolights/>). The joint development of the MetaboLights database for Metabolomics experiments is being discussed, enabling the provision of derived information on cross-species, cross-technique data covering metabolite structures and their reference spectra as well as their biological roles, locations, and concentrations, and experimental data from metabolic experiments. MetaboLights is an ELIXIR (<https://elixir-europe.org/>) deposition database and the recommended repository for metabolomics data for a number of leading journals. MetaboLights is also coordinating MetabolomicsHub, the international Consortium of metabolomics repositories, aiming to standardise open data practices in the field. MetaboLights uses the extensive, robust and secure state-of-the-art computational architecture of the European Bioinformatics Institute (EMBL-EBI). The data handled by EMBL-EBI, including that within MetaboLights, is stored in multiple geographical locations to ensure long-term security and data protection. The EMBL-EBI infrastructure is maintained by expert technical staff, with the EMBL-EBI resources heavily used by researchers worldwide, receiving more than 123 million web requests per day. MetaboLights is an open-access database and repository for metabolomics studies. It provides users with raw MS/NMR experimental data, metadata, metabolite information and reference spectra, which supports the sharing and reuse of experimental data to further advance research in the metabolomics field. Central to this is its alignment with the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable), ensuring that data can be discovered and reused.

Implementation Roadmap

In the preparatory phase, the EIRENE consortium focused on formulation of the scientific challenges, identification of associated research capacity needs and mapping existing service capacities in the EIRENE consortium. This resulted in a detailed map of capacities available across the EIRENE national nodes, describing also their readiness, quality, and development strategy. The services ready to be provided via the centralised EIRENE open access system at the beginning of the implementation period were identified.

Steps of the implementation roadmap

1. Catalogue of Services

Available services will be clustered according to the EIRENE service pillars and organised in the service catalogue. On-going efforts of the PARC Partnership (e.g., existing Chemical Risk Assessment Knowledge Hub, CRA KH) will be leveraged: The CRA KH mapping laboratory capacities, monitoring and biomonitoring efforts, data, and tools will be enhanced and upgraded to provide information on the availability of services. The catalogue will enable registering services of other collaborating RIs and will be regularly updated.

Laboratory services

Special attention will be paid to proper documentation, quality assurance procedures, and compliance with Open Science (availability of SOPs, libraries, data-processing tools, etc.) as a base for future harmonisation and upscaling.

Cohort catalogue

Similarly, a simple catalogue of available cohorts will be developed to serve globally for future harmonisation and collaborative projects. The synergy with the IHEN project will be exploited.

2. Service Access and Management System (single-point access)

To provide access to EIRENE services, the access management system will be fully developed together with the Service access policy. It will allow the registration of all relevant distributed facilities and services listed in the catalogue, matchmaking of applicants to service providers, submission of proposals, support the evaluation process, and implement committee-controlled access to the selected facilities and services, including exchange of contracts, monitoring, and reporting. The development of the EIRENE catalogue of services and open access management system will be the most important goal for the first year of the Implementation period. This effort will be supported by synergistic projects, namely the Teaming project with EIRENE and existing and new INFRA-DEV and INFRA-SERV projects.

3. Provision of Physical, Remote, and Virtual Access to Services

The core principles for providing access to EIRENE services include (i) prioritisation for access being based on scientific merit and technical feasibility (in case of multiple high-quality proposals, the preference is given to new RI users), (ii) making all meta(data) FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable), and (iii) Users retain ownership of their intellectual property rights. The Service access policy will define the process for the establishment of the User Selection Committee to review applications for access, the Panel of Expert Reviewers, and the establishment of the evaluation criteria. First call offering EIRENE open-access services is expected in the second year of the EIRENE implementation.

4. Integration of Services of Other RIs from the ESFRI Landscape and Relevant Projects

The open-access system will enable providing a single-point access to services of multiple research infrastructures from the ESFRI landscape, but also capacities developed in the synergistic international projects (PARC, IHEN, NEXUS, etc.). Special attention will be paid to the development of integrated service and integrated knowledge access. A combination of exposure data with population surveys or clinical trials has the potential to advance health and ageing research in Europe and provide deeper insights into disease aetiology, progression, and treatment response. A translation of data on environmental exposures to knowledge and advice needed for informed policy making and/or decision making in clinical practice will also be pursued. The new INFRA-SERV and INFRA-TECH project opportunities will be leveraged to promote such synergies.

5. Development of new technologies

EIRENE triggers the development of new methods and technologies in many related areas, including automatization and miniaturisation of analytical procedures to increase sensitivity and selectivity of high-resolution screening, new advancements in personal sampling and sensing technologies, new methodologies for non-animal toxicological testing, but especially new generative AI tools for integrating and interpreting multidimensional data. The unique core facilities will not only provide access to excellent research capacities, often unavailable at the national level, but also support the development of a creative environment fostering innovations in the EU and beyond.

1. Increasing the quality, integrity, and openness of research methods and data

EIRENE will continuously enhance the quality and capacity of its infrastructural services while laying the groundwork for innovative solutions to emerging challenges. For example, there is a great need for the development of novel screening methods and the large-scale assessment of human exposure to anthropogenic chemicals. High-throughput procedures will be advanced to rationalise sample preparation and expand suspect and non-targeted screening. A unified framework, based on cutting-edge high-resolution mass spectrometry, will support harmonised chemical profiling of human biosamples to identify biomarkers of exposure and effect. Unlike prior single-site successes (e.g., Olympic Drug Testing Labs, International Phenome Centres), multi-site harmonisation has been hindered by diverse platforms and protocols. Uniquely, EIRENE partners have automated operations, standardised system suitability assessments, and will implement multi-site harmonisation and iterate concordance testing to achieve distributed replication. Robust QA/QC procedures will underpin the transnational deployment of integrated targeted, suspect, and non-targeted analyses, extending the characterisation of internalised exposures and biological responses. Data storage and processing are equally critical for the annotation, identification, and quantification of measured chemicals. While existing tools can extract and identify mass spectral features, most do not enable full reproducibility of results. The Galaxy platform was developed specifically to ease the access and use of software for scientists, providing fully reproducible FAIR data analysis and reporting. However, current tools for processing mass spectrometry data are disconnected and unable to be leveraged in a reusable, modular manner. In partnership with ELIXIR and EBI, EIRENE will extend standardised metadata models and upgrade workflows to become a modular suite of Galaxy tools with interoperable inputs and outputs, reaching a European standard for processing of data from chemical profiling of human biosamples that is fully compliant with international harmonisation, sustainability, and FAIR objectives. Launching these methods in high-throughput facilities will enable a new generation of large-scale studies focused on a better understanding of the impact of various factors on the onset and development of diseases. Such infrastructural capacity will then be applied to screen the sets of well-designed and harmonized cohort studies to ensure adequate statistical power needed for the health impact assessment of combined exposures.

2. Alignment with FAIR principles

Improved data sharing and integration between various human and environmental studies is another important challenge, addressing which would enable the joint interpretation of data across various disciplines and the development of new prediction models, prevention, and intervention strategies. In EIRENE, we will provide a roadmap on data FAIRification and orchestration needed to operationalize current and future physical, remote and virtual access services. However, we will also showcase an exposome data integration to demonstrate the workflow from FAIR data to knowledge for policymakers, focusing on integrating health observation and health data for risk assessment. The outcomes of such efforts will be available to both the scientific community and policymakers to inform evidence-based decision-making for the adequate protection of human health and better healthcare.

3. Standards and ontologies

EIRENE data and metadata models will be designed for interoperability and will be openly accessible whenever possible. Host organisations will be able to determine the level of data access (open, registered, and controlled), which will then be set up in cooperation with e.g., the ELIXIR Beacon Network. Inspired by GA4GH (<https://www.ga4gh.org/>), this will provide convenient access and compatibility across institutions, ERICs, or National Nodes. ‘Access tiers’ will define precise authorization requirements. For example, ‘open access’ Beacons are accessible to anonymous internet users, whereas ‘registered access’ Beacons are accessible only to registered users who have agreed to a set of data use conditions. To facilitate interoperability, the same metadata standards, data standards, vocabularies, and other FAIR Enabling Resources will be used across all EIRENE domains, as much as possible. However, the specific needs of each research domain may require the use of specific solutions for FAIRification. The data strategy will develop recommendations for standards, vocabularies, and other FAIR Enabling Resources to be used across EIRENE. For instance, for the reporting of toxicological omics data, the guidelines of the OECD’s Extended Advisory Group of Molecular Screening and Toxicogenomics will be considered.

4. Open Science practices

Open science is premised upon broad access to scientific knowledge, tools, data, and publications. It promotes accurate verification of scientific results, reduces duplication, and increases efficiency, productivity, cost-effectiveness, collaboration, innovation, and trust in science. EIRENE exemplifies Open Science by integrating previously scattered capacities into a cohesive, widely accessible, and efficient network of open services. It will bring complementary research capacities from across and beyond Europe together to provide excellent services necessary to advance exposome research. Specific attention will be paid to developing harmonised methodologies, quality assurance and quality control mechanisms, as well as analytical and data processing frameworks and reporting standards. Adoption of FAIR Data practices and compliance with EOSC is emphasised, describing the development of the EIRENE framework for collection, curation, harmonisation, and interpretation of data and providing access to them in support of the European Open Science. The open-access guidelines and policies will be available to potential users via the EIRENE web page. Synergies with the European Open Science Cloud, European Health Data Space, and other European data-related efforts will be reinforced.

5. Open data

We will develop and offer the main entry point to the EIRENE data sources for registered users on the EIRENE webpage. A user-friendly web interface, including search tools and relevant criteria, will be developed to search metadata catalogues of all EIRENE domains. It will maintain the metadata catalogues and the links to the original storage place of specific data, as well as tools for data analysis. The access platform will host all services necessary for managing and executing workflows, including dashboards for private computational environments deployed on demand by users. Open-source codes for data processing and dataset submission/annotation will be reinforced as well.

Building the EIRENE user community

The **EIRENE User Forum** will be established to identify the needs and gaps, advertise for available capacities, exploit synergies and co-design new services. A variety of users of EIRENE services have already been identified. They include experts from academia (exposure scientists, toxicologists, epidemiologists, modellers), clinical trials, Horizon Europe projects (IHEN, EnviHealthNet etc.) and Partnerships (including PARC), the NEXUS project and the Global Exposome Forum, RI user communities, JRC facilities, public health, and environment authorities (regulators, hazard and risk assessors), EU agencies (EEA, EChA, EFSA, ECDC), international organisations (OECD, UNEP, WHO), professionals from relevant sectors (healthcare, insurance, urban planning, informatics), pharmaceutical, chemical and biomedical industries (including SMEs), policymakers, NGOs, and the general public.

The nature of EIRENE services will require active engagement with multiple other stakeholders active in the field, including other ESFRI infrastructures active in the Environment and Health & Food domains and laboratories operating within the Joint Research Centre, relevant partnerships and Horizon Europe projects emerging from the recent and future calls. They will all be considered in the communication and outreach activities mapping available capacities and emerging needs, stakeholders' and users' consultations. The stakeholder surveys will be conducted at national, European, and global levels to aim at identifying users' communities, understanding their priorities, responding to their needs by developing innovative services, and creating future demand for such services. The EIRENE communication plan will target various groups of users and stakeholders using multiple communication channels (EIRENE website, newsletters, social media, events, training, presentations at conferences, publications, and communications to various target groups including prospective partners and users).

Training

The development of services and user communities must be complemented by the development of human resources. The EIRENE training modules will be developed addressing both the training needs of service providers and users' communities based on RIs demands skilled and competent personnel and stakeholders' surveys. The training modules will address the need to develop the curriculum as a tool for the education and training of a new generation of RI operators and technicians. Existing training modules available in participating RIs will be exploited/upscaled, e.g. series of exposome summer schools and boot camps available through the EIRENE partners. The high-quality HR development practices contributing to building openness, transparency, respect, equality, and cooperation will be reinforced and maintained.

Innovations and Impacts

The implementation of EIRENE is expected to generate significant impacts through enhanced access to novel scientific services and integrated knowledge, strengthened problem-solving capacities, biomedical innovations, improved environmental management and policy, and more effective responses to societal challenges. To further enhance these impacts, the project

will establish dedicated communication channels with diverse stakeholder groups to inform and guide future developments. It will support the integration of services and develop structured processes for their co-design with stakeholder and user communities and testing their feasibility in demonstrators showcasing scientific excellence in H&E research in Europe. In the implementation phase, we will specifically focus on the development of a sustainable model for the long-term provision of EIRENE services. This model will comprehensively address all relevant aspects, including: **Financial sustainability** (maintenance and development needs, complementarities and synergies, joint efforts, and potential funding sources), **Human resource development**, with a focus on building interdisciplinary capacities through training programmes, summer schools, and joint curricula, **Socioeconomic impact maximization**, drawing on the Research Infrastructures' Impact Assessment Toolkit and employing both quantitative and qualitative approaches. The exploitation of EIRENE services by industry will be promoted with flexible access schemes, clear IP and technology transfer support regarding licensing and usage rights, and training programs to enable companies to rapidly adopt and integrate collaborative services into their R&D pipelines.

Sustainability

EIRENE aims to deliver sufficient capacity of multidisciplinary infrastructural services needed for scientific investigation of environmental impacts on human health. Access to services will enable leading-edge scientific investigation and provide comprehensive data to support evidence-informed decision-making and to secure a competitive advantage for European industries. The project focuses on the speedy deployment of existing services and substantial enhancement of quality, capacity, and integration of participating (and new) research infrastructures.

A common sustainability strategy will be developed followed by a more detailed Sustainability Plan covering expected cost structure, pricing options, and revenue streams for a EIRENE continuity. The risk analysis and mitigation plan addressing technical obsolescence, research priorities, funding gaps, regulatory changes etc. will be an important part of the Sustainability Plan. Cross-project interaction and experience from previous and ongoing INFRA-SERV projects and insights regarding their governance models, service provision and alignment with EU policy priorities will help developing the sustainability strategy in alignment with the RI landscape. Synergy with and output from stakeholder engagement and impact demonstration will help reinforce the resilience of the EIRENE Sustainability Plan.

Societal impacts

Several application areas of this holistic approach have been identified in the report of the European Parliament's Panel for the Future of Science and Technology (STOA) presented to the European Parliament in 2025. In the **chemical domain**, exposomics enables the assessment of real-world exposures, including cumulative and low-dose effects of industrial pollutants, supporting regulations like REACH, the Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability, and the Clean Industrial Deal. In the field of **child health**, exposomics contribute to the identification of early-life environmental risk, such as air pollution and endocrine disruptors, that shape long-term health trajectories, aligning with the European Child Guarantee and WHO's strategy on child and adolescent health. For **occupational health**, it facilitates the monitoring of hazardous workplace exposures and anticipates risks associated with emerging

industrial processes, informing the EU Strategic Framework on Health and Safety at Work. The holistic concept of the exposome also addresses the “triple crisis” of **chemical pollution, climate change, and biodiversity loss** by evaluating health risks linked to e.g., heat stress, air pollution, wildfires, and ecosystem changes, including impacts on food production. These insights directly inform adaptation policies such as the 2040 European Climate Law and the One Health Strategy. In **urban planning**, exposomics supports the identification of air and noise pollution sources and the assessment of environmental quality in both indoor and outdoor settings, contributing to the development of healthier, more sustainable cities in line with the European Strategy for Housing and Construction, the Sustainable Transport Investment Plan, the Climate Adaptation Plan, and the New European Bauhaus. Exposomics also empowers **citizens** by providing exposure data that supports informed health decisions, public awareness, and participatory governance, reflecting priorities under the European Green Deal and Real Deal Project. Translation of exposomics to **clinical practice** enhances precision medicine by uncovering environmental drivers of disease, contributing to early diagnosis, prevention, and personalised treatment approaches aligned with initiatives such as the Mental Health Plan and EU Mission on Cancer. This also opens a door to biomedical innovations and increased European competitiveness.

Additional resources to be leveraged

EIRENE will leverage synergies with two important projects that are currently being implemented under Horizon Europe, IHEN and PARC. **IHEN** (<https://humanexposome.net/>) is a European initiative that aims to coordinate and support exposome research across Europe and beyond. It focuses on establishing a shared vision and roadmap for the future of exposome science and aligns these efforts with international partners. IHEN key activities include facilitating access to population cohorts, centralised cataloguing of software tools and resources, and developing dedicated training programmes for the next generation of exposome researchers. While IHEN is centred on advancing the research agenda, it does not focus on building the physical and virtual research infrastructure needed to support exposome science at scale. This is where IHEN works closely with EIRENE, which is focused on developing the infrastructure required to deliver on the ambitions of the exposome community, ensuring Europe is equipped to meet future research and policy needs in environmental health. Together, IHEN and EIRENE ensure that Europe’s exposome research ecosystem is both scientifically visionary and practically enabled. Both IHEN and EIRENE build on the European Human Exposome Network (**EHEN**, <https://humanexposome.net/>), the Horizon 2020 cluster of 9 human exposome projects developing necessary tools for exposome research. Additional knowledge, tools, and capacities to advance exposomics were, or are being, developed in the H2020 and Horizon Europe project clusters (e.g., EURION cluster on endocrine disruption, IDEAL cluster on air pollution and health, EXPOHEALTHNET on the role of environmental pollution in non-communicable diseases), Joint Projects (Human BioMonitoring for Europe, HBM4EU). EIRENE will provide access to some of the tools, capacities, and data developed in EHEN, and the EHEN/IHEN communities also represent the largest communities of potential users of EIRENE services. IHEN and EIRENE closely collaborate with **NEXUS**, supported by the National Institutes of Health (NIH), to connect international stakeholders and streamline communication and training activities for exposomics. NEXUS is designed to operationalise the exposome by advancing measurement and modelling technologies and applying them to human health outcomes. It is working to transform the entire biomedical and public health enterprise by inculcating the importance of comprehensive and systematic analysis of the environmental drivers of health and disease.

Efforts under NEXUS that are well aligned with the goals of EIRENE including (i) establishing a framework for exposomics analysis of biological and environmental samples, (ii) developing a framework for geospatial-based exposomics studies of environmental and social influences on health and disease including a scalable geospatial data science and research infrastructure, and (iii) creating a comprehensive exposomics digital framework to support precision environmental health. NEXUS works with global partners to establish the universal standards for exposomics profiling that integrate digital, biological, and geospatial markers to make exposome-wide association studies (ExWAS) a reality for studies of all human diseases. It is therefore of great strategic importance to bring the leaders of NEXUS service provision (Columbia University and PNNL) to the EIRENE consortium and make their resources available to European scientists for better global coordination and exploitation of knowledge for innovations.

In 2025, NEXUS, IHEN and EIRENE jointly organized the **Exposome Moonshot meeting** in Washington, D.C., which aimed to establish the **Global Exposome Forum**, an international effort to advance exposome science globally. As human exposures vary significantly among the regions and populations, specific attention was paid to geographical coverage when inviting potential participants. The need for technological innovations, harmonisation of scientific approaches and research tools, documented quality assurance/quality control measures, enhanced availability of data and AI tools, and capacity building and training opportunities to support regions lacking capacities were discussed in multiple break-out sessions. These international consultations highlighted the need to further enhance infrastructural capacities by developing new high-throughput technologies and harmonised analytical and data processing tools to be applied across clinical and population studies, and to coordinate provision of open-access services across multiple domains, ongoing projects and existing infrastructures. The Global Exposome Forum provides a platform for integration of all geographical regions, extending global reach and collaborators beyond Europe and the US. This aligns with the EIRENE ambitions to build global capacities for exposomics. The platform will be very valuable for EIRENE's global outreach, user and stakeholder engagement, and will be leveraged in the EIRENE implementation phase.

Many of EIRENE's partners have been actively participating in **PARC** (and the previous Horizon 2020 Joint Programme Human BioMonitoring for Europe, HBM4EU). PARC strives to establish an EU-wide risk assessment hub of excellence. It requires the construction of a cross-disciplinary network to identify research and innovation needs and to support research uptake into regulatory chemical risk assessment. PARC research and innovation activities are designed to respond to identified priorities in support of current regulatory risk assessment processes for chemical substances and to emerging challenges, and to strengthen existing capacities and build new transdisciplinary platforms to support chemical risk assessment. Recognising the crucial role of the underlying infrastructures for the future sustainability of all PARC efforts is a major advancement reflecting lessons learned from the previous HBM4EU Joint Programme. Several work packages in PARC focus on identifying, inventorying, and harmonising potential infrastructural capacities, namely laboratory capacities, environmental monitoring, biomonitoring networks, population studies, relevant databases, data-related services, and modelling tools. While this is a major step forward, PARC itself cannot (i) ensure the future sustainability of these newly developed resources and (ii) make them available to the community outside PARC. Therefore, a strong link has already been established between PARC and EIRENE, making sure that these two efforts are well aligned and benefit from each other. PARC is specifically focused on chemical exposures and associated risks, whilst IHEN/EHEN address environmental exposures more holistically, but both need access to similar infrastructure: laboratories for the assessment of exposure and

effect markers, monitoring and biomonitoring networks and population studies, hazard and risk assessment models, and computational frameworks for integrating environmental, population and socioeconomic data. The alignment of PARC and IHEN/EHEN efforts, roadmaps and phase-out strategies with the strategic development of EIRENE and other ESFRI RIs providing complementary services (BBMRI, EATRIS, ELIXIR etc.) is crucially important. This is also true for other clusters of current and future human exposome-related projects (such as IDEAL or ENVIHEATLHNET). They should all be important elements of the EIRENE community of practice developed within this project.

Synergies to be exploited

During EIRENE PPP, we have worked on the positioning of EIRENE in the ERA and ESFRI landscapes. EIRENE has joined both the ENVRI board of the environmental RIs and the LS-RI life sciences cluster of RIs, as well as the ERIC Forum. We initiated discussions on synergies and complementarities, and on future opportunities for joint development of services with multiple RIs, including BBMRI, ELIXIR, ECRIN, EATRIS, SHARE, EuroBioImaging, INSTRUCT, AnaEE, ACTRIS, and EMBRC. This resulted in multiple joint projects such as the FHERITALE project (with INSTRUCT and AnaEE) mapping capacities for research on micro- and nanoplastics, Integrate-LMedC (with BBMRI and ECRIN) addressing European medical cohorts, EOSC4CANCER (with e.g. BBMRI) supporting the implementation of the EOSC, or IRISCC (with e.g. ACTRIS) building integrative services linking air quality to health.

These initial discussions also led to the development of the joint INFRA-SERV proposal SIRENE, which was submitted in September 2025, mobilising EIRENE infrastructural capacities in 16 European countries, Canada, and the USA, together with those of the ten ESFRI Landmarks from the Health and Food, Environment, and Social domains. **BBMRI-ERIC's** (Biobanking and Biomolecular Resources RI) mission is to establish, operate, and develop a pan-European distributed research infrastructure to facilitate access to these resources and facilities and to support high-quality biomolecular and medical research, offering cutting-edge services to address fundamental research questions. In SIRENE, BBMRI will provide access to data and samples from clinical and population studies to be combined with the EIRENE cohorts, biomolecular services, and advanced computing services and IT tools developed to support the exposome research in the EHEN project HEAP. SIRENE will also involve **ECRIN-ERIC** (the European Clinical Research Infrastructure Network), facilitating multinational clinical trials. It consists of national networks of clinical trial units with expertise in study design, study management (regulatory and ethics, monitoring, vigilance), data management, and analysis. ECRIN services are certified ISO-9001-2015, and to date, it has a portfolio of over 79 clinical trials and 40 infrastructure development projects. ECRIN and BBMRI will benefit from the human exposome-related services introduced in SIRENE as they can add a new dimension to their ongoing studies. ECRIN will therefore lead one of the SIRENE demonstration studies testing the feasibility of linking clinical and exposomics research. The third member of the European Alliance of the Medical Research Infrastructures (EU-AMRI) participating in this project is **EATRIS-ERIC** (European Infrastructure for Translational Medicine). EATRIS brings together resources and services to translate scientific discoveries into patient benefits. It focuses on the pre-clinical and early clinical development of drugs, vaccines, and diagnostics. Solutions are developed in the fields of advanced therapy, medicinal products, imaging and tracing, small molecules, vaccines, and biomarkers. EATRIS brings translational medicine expertise, particularly multiomics-related services, which complement the target and non-target chemical agent analyses available through the EIRENE consortium. For the development of new online

services, the involvement of **ELIXIR** (European Life-science Infrastructure for Biological Information) is strategic as it provides access to Galaxy, an open-source platform that allows researchers to analyse and share scientific data using various user-friendly web-based interfaces. Galaxy is a multi-user environment that facilitates the sharing of tools, workflows, and data with others, which makes it particularly easy to reproduce results, verify their correctness, and enable other researchers to build upon them in future studies. In SIRENE, the Galaxy environment will be used for the development of data-processing pipelines for chemical agents and metabolomics. Capacities in multi-omics will also be accessible via **EMBL**, and specifically through EMBL-EBI, which hosts core molecular biology databases, integrated for multi-omics knowledge mining. SIRENE will also benefit from EMBL-EBI's longstanding involvement in developing and delivering on the training strategy of research infrastructures, frequently in close collaboration with ESFRI research infrastructures, in its capacity as an ELIXIR node. **EURO-BIOIMAGING-ERIC**, the gateway to European biological and biomedical imaging, offers potential SIRENE users open access to imaging technologies and related services, providing scientists with a gateway to cutting-edge biological and biomedical imaging technologies, including access to expertise, data services, and training. Euro-BioImaging has grown to 41 national nodes representing 247 individual imaging facilities in 18 European countries and EMBL, receiving more than 1000 user access requests annually. Euro-BioImaging's services are transversally applicable in biomedicine and can be combined with other RI services addressing the biological effects of environmental exposures. Similarly, **INSTRUCT-ERIC** (European Infrastructure for Integrated Structural Biology) provides open access to a wide range of integrated structural biology techniques applicable to studying how environmental factors affect biological systems. In SIRENE, Instruct will offer prospective users access to wide-ranging facilities from Electron Microscopy to Mass Spectrometry and NMR. In line with the One-health approach, SIRENE extends the scope of services to also cover the environmental domain represented by **ACTRIS-ERIC** (the Aerosol, Clouds, and Trace Gases research infrastructure), producing high-quality data and information on short-lived atmospheric constituents and on the processes leading to the variability of these constituents in natural and controlled atmospheres. ACTRIS enables free access to high-quality long-term atmospheric data, which can enrich available information on air quality as one of the important exposure factors determining human health but, in this project, it also provides access to exposure simulation chambers to be used to get a better insight to exposure pathways. Simulation chambers and other experimental facilities enabling studies in the ecosystems will also be available through **AnaEE-ERIC** (Analysis and Experimentation on Ecosystems), Europe's largest research network for experimental ecology and climate change research, featuring 60+ highly instrumented installations providing services for ecosystem ecology studies under various pressures: climate change, land management, pollution, and biodiversity impacts. All continental ecosystems are represented, including tropical, mountain, wetland, forest, freshwater, and agro-ecosystems. The last pan-European RI acting at the E&H interface is **EMBRC-ERIC** (European Marine Biological Resource Centre), which aims to answer fundamental questions regarding the health of oceanic ecosystems in a changing environment, enable new technologies to further our investigation capabilities, support life-science breakthrough discoveries with the use of marine biological models, and continue long-term marine monitoring efforts. It is a driver in the development of blue biotechnologies and will provide access to capacities supporting both fundamental and applied research activities for sustainable solutions in the food, health and environmental sectors. A very important contribution is expected from the EU **Joint Research Centre** (JRC), which has already expressed a strong interest in collaborating on the proposal if successful. JRC can enable access to its research infrastructures and resources for hazard and risk assessment, and its

wastewater surveillance portfolio for various application fields from One-Health through biosecurity and water resilience. Specific attention will be paid to the alignment of the SIRENE efforts with the **IPCHEM**, the Information Platform for Chemical Monitoring maintained by JRC, as the reference access point for locating and retrieving chemical occurrence data across various media (e.g., environment, human, food/feed, indoor air, and products) in the European Union. IPCHEM was developed to provide information on exposure to chemicals and their burden on the human body and the environment and continues to support a coordinated approach for collecting, storing, accessing, and evaluating data related to the occurrence of chemicals and chemical mixtures. This collaboration with JRC will also ensure the link to the future European Common Data Platform on Chemicals (**CDPC**). **SHARE-ERIC** (Survey of Health, Ageing, and Retirement in Europe) which studies the effects of health, social, economic, and environmental policies over the life-course of European citizens bring an important focus on social aspects into the SIRENE consortium. SHARE is the largest pan-European social science panel study, providing internationally comparable longitudinal microdata, which allows insights into the fields of public health and socio-economic living conditions of the ageing European population. It is harmonized within a global network of ageing surveys and has become an essential tool for evidence-based policymaking. At the same time, SHARE is an important stakeholder of SIRENE, since new exposure assessment-related services have potential to significantly enhance the scope of data collected through the SHARE surveys.

Annex 1. Readily available EIRENE Service

Country	Institution	Service	Type of access
Austria	University of Vienna	Mass Spec Center	TNA
Austria	University of Vienna	Mass Spec Center	TNA
Belgium	Katholic University Leuven	LCMSMS	TNA
Belgium	Katholic University Leuven	HSSP	VA
Belgium	University of Antwerpen	EIRENE-Flanders	TNA
Belgium	VITO	PARC Aligned Studies	VA
Belgium	VITO	HBM4EU aligned studies	VA
Belgium	VITO	3xG birth cohort	VA
Belgium	VITO	FLEHS program	VA
Belgium	VITO	VITO-HBM; VITO-HEALTH	VA
Belgium	VITO	O-link proteomics	TNA
Belgium	VITO	Platform for in vitro inhalation testing	TNA
Canada	University of Alberta	Exposome 1.0 Kit	TNA
Canada	University of Alberta	Exposome 2.0 Kit	TNA
Canada	University of Alberta	Exposome 3.0 Kit	TNA

Canada	University of Alberta	University of Alberta	VA
Cyprus	CUT	Untargeted GC-MS metabolomics	TNA
Cyprus	CUT	CHILDRENFIRST COHORT (Data service unit)	VA
Cyprus	CUT	Circadian Rhythm Markers	TNA
Cyprus	CUT	Access to paediatric samples and/or datasets	TNA
Cyprus	CUT	Non Pharma Precision (Chrono) Health Intervention Study	TNA
Czech Republic	Masaryk University	CELSPAC Biobank - automated nucleic acid extraction (DNA/RNA isolation)	TNA
Czech Republic	Masaryk University	CELSPAC Biobank - exposome cohort samples with metadata	TNA
Czech Republic	Masaryk University	CELSPAC Biobank - multiplex IgE analyses	TNA
Czech Republic	Masaryk University	CELSPAC Cohort - access to data	VA
Czech Republic	Masaryk University	RECETOX Trace analytical laboratory (TAL)	TNA
Czech Republic	Masaryk University	RECETOX Trace analytical laboratory (TAL)	TNA
Czech Republic	Masaryk University	RECETOX Trace analytical laboratory (TAL)	TNA
Czech Republic	Masaryk University	RECETOX microbiome laboratory (MGL)	TNA
Czech Republic	Masaryk University	RECETOX microbiome laboratory (MGL)	TNA
Czech Republic	Masaryk University	RECETOX RI Data services - GENASIS	VA
Czech Republic	Masaryk University	2D Biocompatibility/ Cytotoxicity assays	TNA
Czech Republic	Masaryk University	3D Cytotoxicity and spheroid growth (GILA)	TNA
Czech Republic	Masaryk University	3D Organ toxicity	TNA
Czech Republic	Masaryk University	Interaction with receptors relevant for endocrine disruption	TNA
Czech Republic	Masaryk University	Steroidogenesis assay	TNA
Czech Republic	Masaryk University	ED - Thyroid	TNA
Czech Republic	Masaryk University	Non-genotoxic carcinogenicity assay	TNA
Czech Republic	Masaryk University	MS data processing software tools & data resources	VA
Czech Republic	Masaryk University	LC-HRMS small molecules	TNA
Czech Republic	Masaryk University	Inflammatory & Immunity protein quant.	TNA
Czech Republic	Masaryk University	GC-HRMS metabolite profiling	TNA
Czech Republic	Masaryk University	GC-HRMS anthropogenic profiling	TNA
Czech Republic	Masaryk University	BAL-training	TNA
France	EHESP	PFAS quant.	TNA
France	EHESP	Urinary pesticide quant.	TNA
France	EHESP	Metals quant.	TNA
France	EHESP	Glyphosate urine quant.	TNA
France	INSERM	Cohort operational maintenance	VA
France	INSERM	Cohort integration	VA
France	ONIRIS - LABERCA	BPx Urine	TNA

France	ONIRIS - LABERCA	Diox PCB - serum	TNA
France	ONIRIS - LABERCA	Diox PCB -RFB	TNA
France	ONIRIS - LABERCA	HAP-OH Urine	TNA
France	ONIRIS - LABERCA	PFAS Lait maternal	TNA
France	ONIRIS - LABERCA	Phtalates - urine	TNA
France	ONIRIS - LABERCA	POC serum	TNA
France	ONIRIS - LABERCA	RFB serum	TNA
Germany	HGMU	NAKO (basic data)	VA
Germany	HGMU	NAKO (Env. Data)	VA
Germany	HGMU	NAKO (exposomics)	VA
Germany	HGMU	NAKO (exposomics_new)	VA
Germany	HGMU	NAKO (exposomics_max)	VA
Germany	HGMU	NAKO (gen. data)	VA
Germany	HGMU	NAKO (GxE int.)	VA
Greece	AUTH	Targeted Profiling (Multicomponent Methods)	TNA
Greece	AUTH	Untargeted Profiling (Omics, Exposomics, SS, NTS)	TNA
Greece	AUTH	INTEGRA SYSTEM	VA
Greece	AUTH	PARC SSbD Toolbox	VA
Greece	AUTH	HERACLES multi-omics for toxicological studies (transcriptomics - metabolomics - joint pathway analysis)	TNA
Greece	AUTH	Animal house facility for in vivo testing	TNA
Greece	AUTH	Micro- and nano-plastics (MPs) ex-vivo, in-vivo, in-vitro detection and identification	TNA
Greece	AUTH	General Population Exposome Cohorts	VA
Greece	AUTH	Intervention Exposome Cohorts	VA
Greece	AUTH	Exposure and Health Examination Survey (EXHES) Greek Cohort	VA
Greece	AUTH	Occupational Studies	VA
Greece	AUTH	General Population Exposome Cohorts	TNA
Greece	AUTH	Intervention Exposome Cohorts	TNA
Greece	AUTH	Exposure and Health Examination Survey (EXHES) Greek Cohort	TNA
Greece	AUTH	Occupational Studies	TNA
Greece	NHRF	Genomics facility	TNA
Greece	NHRF	Proteomics facility	TNA
Greece	NHRF	Metabolomics facility	TNA
Greece	NHRF	Cryo-EM facility	TNA
Greece	NHRF	Animal House with advanced PET imaging	TNA
Italy	CNR	CNR BEH Labs	TNA

Italy	CNR	GOS4M Knowledge Hub	VA
Italy	ISS	ISS Trace Labs	TNA
Luxembourg	LNS	Pesticides quant.	TNA
Luxembourg	LNS	Phthalates quant.	TNA
Luxembourg	LNS	HBM_SPMA, SBMA quant.	TNA
Luxembourg	LNS	HBM_Metals quant.	TNA
Luxembourg	LNS	HBM_Bisphenol quant.	TNA
Luxembourg	LNS	HBM_BFR quant	TNA
Luxembourg	LNS	PFAS quant.	TNA
Netherlands	RIVM	MCRA	VA
Netherlands	Leiden University	Exposome Scan - Metabolomics and Analytics Centre (MAC)	TNA
Netherlands	Leiden University	Exposome Scan - Metabolomics and Analytics Centre (MAC)	TNA
Netherlands	Leiden University	Exposome Scan - Metabolomics and Analytics Centre (MAC)	TNA
Netherlands	Leiden University	LACDR	TNA
Netherlands	Leiden University	LADCR	VA
Netherlands	UMCG	MOLGENIS FAIR data catalog or registry	VA
Netherlands	UMCG	MOLGENIS DataSHIELD service	VA
Netherlands	UMCG	Lifelines cohort	TNA
Netherlands	Utrecht University	PIAMA cohort	VA
Netherlands	Utrecht University	Nightingale Cohort	VA
Netherlands	Utrecht University	AMIGO cohort	VA
Netherlands	Utrecht University	Exposome-Maps	VA
Netherlands	Utrecht University	Air quality mobile measurement platforms	TNA
Netherlands	Utrecht University	EPIC-Cohort	VA
Netherlands	Vrije University	Exposome Non-target suspect screening	TNA
Netherlands	Vrije University	Exposome/HBM Targeted analysis	TNA
Netherlands	Vrije University	Microplastic analysis	TNA
Netherlands	Vrije University	HT-EDA platform	TNA
Netherlands	Vrije University	Histology	TNA
Netherlands	Wageningen University	Exposome - suspect/non target screening LC-HRMS	TNA
Netherlands	Wageningen University	Exposome - suspect/non target screening GC-HRMS	TNA
Netherlands	Wageningen University	target analysis multi-method pesticides	TNA
Netherlands	Wageningen University	target analysis glyphosate/AMPA	TNA
Netherlands	Wageningen University	target analysis multi-method mycotoxins	TNA
Slovenia	Jozef Stefan Institute	Stable isotope analysis	TNA
Slovenia	Jozef Stefan Institute	Speciation analysis	TNA

Slovenia	Jozef Stefan Institute	Metal isotope analysis - multicollector	TNA
Slovenia	Jozef Stefan Institute	Stable isotope analysis	TNA
Slovenia	Jozef Stefan Institute	ICP-MS multielement analysis	TNA
Slovenia	Jozef Stefan Institute	Stable isotope analysis	TNA
Slovenia	Jozef Stefan Institute	Speciation analysis	TNA
Slovenia	Jozef Stefan Institute	Metal isotope analysis - multicollector	TNA
Slovenia	Jozef Stefan Institute	GC-MS analysis - phthalates in urine	TNA
Slovenia	Jozef Stefan Institute	LC-MS analysis - bisphenols in urine	TNA
Slovenia	Jozef Stefan Institute	LC-HRMS analysis - metabolomics, exposure screening	TNA
Slovenia	Jozef Stefan Institute	In-vitro microbiome assays	TNA
Slovenia	Jozef Stefan Institute	ICP-MS multielement analysis	TNA
Slovenia	Jozef Stefan Institute	Isolation of DNA from blood or saliva + genotyping	TNA
Slovenia	Jozef Stefan Institute	GC-MS - volatile organic biomarker analysis	TNA
Slovenia	Jozef Stefan Institute	Full genome sequencing	TNA
Spain	ISGloba	Exposome Cohorts	VA
Sweden	Orebro University	Chemical Pollutant analysis	TNA
Sweden	Orebro University	Bioanalytical platform (in vitro)	TNA
Sweden	Orebro University	In-vivo toxicity models for aquatic and terrestrial systems	TNA
Sweden	SLU	Water pollution analysis (target/nontarget) and EDA platform	TNA
Sweden	SLU	Development Biology Platform SLU	TNA
Sweden	Stockholm University	SciLifeLab National Facility for Exposomics	TNA
Sweden	Stockholm University	Ecotoxicological Effect Assessment Facility	TNA
Sweden	Stockholm University	DNA adductomics	TNA
Switzerland	University of Geneva	Untargeted cellular profiling (30 samples)	TNA
Switzerland	University of Geneva	Untargeted cellular profiling (60 samples)	TNA
Switzerland	University of Geneva	Blood steroidomics (30 samples)	TNA
UK	University of Birmingham	Phenome Centre Birmingham	TNA
UK	University of Birmingham	Phenome Centre Birmingham	VA
UK	University of Birmingham	NAMs and Organ-on-a-chip development	TNA
UK	University of Birmingham	Ecotoxicity with Daphnia, plants and soil microbes	TNA
UK	University of Birmingham	Toxicology data management services	VA
UK	University of Birmingham	In vitro Barrier models	TNA
US	Columbia University	Exposomics Core - LC/GC HRMS	TNA
US	PNNL	Reference-Free Structural Identification of Unknown Molecules	TNA
US	PNNL	Targeted Proteomics	TNA
US	PNNL	Untargeted GC-MS Metabolomics	TNA

US	PNNL	Untargeted LC-MS Lipidomics	TNA
US	PNNL	Untargeted LC-MS Metabolomics	TNA
US	PNNL	Untargeted NMR Metabolomics	TNA
US	PNNL	Untargeted Proteomics	TNA
US	PNNL	Advanced Interactive Data Visualization	VA
US	PNNL	Data Integration and Analysis	VA
US	PNNL	Pathway and Enrichment Analysis	VA
US	PNNL	Statistical Analysis for Biomarkers and Data Trends	VA